

EARTH SCIENCES

ESTIMATION OF THE RIVER REGIME AS A RESULT OF A CHANGE IN CLIMATIC PARAMETERS

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Abstract

The focus and goal of this effort are to evaluate how the regime of climatic factors has changed and how it has affected the regime of river flow. The evaluation technique is based on the utilization of long-term and intra-annual observational data on air temperature, precipitation, and water discharge. In order to analyze observational data, long-term series of observed parameters were plotted and statistical analysis was used.

The study's principal findings include an examination of the dynamics of average annual values of air temperature, precipitation, and water flow from 1960 to 2019. According to the evaluation, there has been a 2.0-2.5°C increase in air temperature in recent years. The analysis of a long-term series of data revealed that the trend line of average precipitation values remained virtually constant over the whole observed time. An assessment of the fluctuations in the average annual water flows of the rivers of the Surkhandarya basin over a long period of time revealed no change in the average values of water discharges, either decreasing or increasing. However, assessments of the intra-annual distribution of atmospheric precipitation and water flow have revealed that there has been a shift in maximum precipitation values from winter to spring in recent years, as well as a shift in water flow from July-August to June-July. Simultaneously, a study of river feeding types revealed that in recent years, the indicator of feeding type began to fall from 0.30, corresponding to snow-glacial feeding, to 0.10, corresponding to snow-rain feeding.

The main conclusion of this work is to establish the impact of climate change on the intra-annual regime of precipitation and water flow in rivers, as well as on changes in the type of river feeding. The main factor behind these changes is an increase in air temperature.

Keywords: climate, river runoff, precipitation, air temperature

All over the world, climate change is recognized as the global problem of the century, which soon can practically change the living conditions familiar to mankind. Each region or even the mainland can undergo significant changes in its natural conditions. Manifestations of the negative impact of climate change for different regions may be different, as well as its scale. Regardless of the causes of climate change, around which there are many discussions, each region must take all possible measures to prevent the negative effects of climate change and adapt to all its negative manifestations (Sh.Sh. Mukhamedjanov, 2015).

Recently all over the world active study of the problems associated with the vulnerability of the economy and the population under climate change are going on. Herewith, researched and developed various scenarios of climate change and the ways which to really adapt for them (S.R. Ibatulin, et al., 2009). However, everyone is wondering how the threat of climate change is real and what is its scope of influence? As noted in the Report of the First Working Group of the Fifth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change: "Each of the last three decades was characterized by a higher temperature at the earth's surface than any other decade since 1850" (IPCC, 5AR, WG1, 2013).

Russian scientists meantime noted that the global temperature change in the twentieth century and the beginning of the XXI century has been uneven. There are three time intervals: warming within 1910-1945 years,

poor cold snap within 1946-1975 years and the most intense warming after 1976. Particular attention is paid to data from the last 30-40 years (V.A. Vladimirov & Y.I. Churakov, 2014).

What are the current trends of climate change for the planet as a whole and particularly in Central Asia? There is no unified opinion, as climatologists have to consider too many factors. More often, they talk about future warming, but deviations in the direction of cold snap also conceivable. Beginning of the twentieth century, it was characterized by a twenty-year cold period (within 1911-1930 years), followed by a continued increase in average temperatures. According to the reconstruction of Vladimir Klimenko, the average temperature in the cold era of the beginning of the twentieth century compared with the period of 1981-2000 years. The Central Asia was colder by 0.5-1.5 °C. depending on the region; average summer temperatures were also colder by 0,0-1,5 °C. Winter temperatures in 1911-1930 years are different from the winter temperatures of 80-90-ies. Therefore, the twentieth century, was much more in the direction of cold snap than the summer (by 1-3 °C) (V.V. Klimenko, 2001).

According to the 13 weather stations with observation period of about 100 years, the increase of the average annual temperature within 1884-1994 years for Uzbekistan was established positive temperature trend, which increased oscillatory manner and consistent with fluctuations in global temperature since 1930s. Trend magnitude of warming, calculated for 100 years of the

twentieth century, are in the range 0,5-1 ° C. (S.K. Alamanov, et al., 2006 (15).

On the territory of Uzbekistan were registered significant variations in annual precipitation, while the average for the territory observed weak tendency to increase them. (V.E. Chub, 2007 16).

In any case, climate change is acknowledged as the century's biggest issue and could soon significantly alter humankind's standard of living. The natural conditions of each region, or even continent, may undergo significant changes. Different regions may experience the negative effects of climate change in different ways, and to varying degrees. Each region should take all reasonable precautions to prevent the negative effects of climate change and adapt to all its negative manifestations, regardless of the causes of climate change, which are the subject of numerous discussions.

On the rivers in Central Asia, sudden variations in water flow have been noticed recently. Runoff fluctuates dramatically from year to year, either decreasing or increasing. Such abrupt shifts can only be the result of the quick melting of glaciers and snow in the winter months with an increase in temperature and a drop in the amount of snowfall, taking into account the sources of saturation of the Central Asian rivers. The recent changes in the local climate, particularly during the winter and spring seasons, are to blame for all variations in river flow. The type of river feeding, and the river flow regime can change as a result of warm winters and heavy spring rains. The goal of this research is to evaluate changes in the regime of climatic factors and their influence on changes in the regime of river flow. The major premise of the work that led our activities to investigate this topic is the idea that we are currently in the early stages of changing both the climatic conditions of the region and the way of development of the river runoff of all Central Asian rivers. A shift in maximum values of atmospheric precipitation is already occurring, which leads to a shift in maximum water discharges; as the winter season warms, the type of river flow feeding switches from snow-glacial to snow-rain. A change in the type of feeding in the near future might result in a dramatic shift in the river flow regime. The majority of the river flow will occur in the spring, with a portion of the flow created in the winter with high water flows. Rain floods will cause runoff to build quickly and with massive water discharges, as is currently common for the summer months. It will be impossible to maintain such a discharge in winter and spring since Central Asian reservoirs are intended for progressive filling, taking into account slow runoff from melting snow and ice. This will result in drought during the summer, when demand for water is highest.

Observed increases in global average surface temperature, frequency and intensity of heat waves and droughts, changes in precipitation frequency and intensity, reduced snow cover, widespread melting of ice, and changes in soil moisture and runoff are some of the key documented hydrologic changes often associated with global climate change (Huber and Knutti, 2011, IPCC, 2014, IPCC, 2008, NCA, 2014a, NCA, 2014b) - 3.

For summer and fall, more frequent and severe seasonal drought is projected (Horton et al., 2014, NCA, 2014b)- 4.

The intra-annual distribution of precipitation and air temperature determines the hydrological regime of rivers and how it changes. The levels of river runoff and their water supply are impacted by variations in certain weather conditions. Anticipated increases in the frequency and intensity of extreme weather events will in turn alter streamflow patterns affecting the operations and downstream hydrologic impacts of existing water infrastructure (Asadieh et al., 2016, Asadieh and Krakauer, 2015, McDaniels et al., 2008, Pahl-Wostl, 2006)-1 and may result in flooding events that will exceed the design limits of dams (Jothityangkoon et al., 2013, Madsen et al., 2014,-5 Najibi et al., 2017-6). The melting of glaciers and snows in mountainous locations during the winter and early spring results in a change in river flow regime and a shift in the maximum flow of water in rivers from summer to spring. The actions of the maintenance services will be complicated as a result of the delay in the maximum flow of rivers in the spring. Yet, even under the current levels of climate variability, water managers are struggling, as increasingly large flood and drought damages proliferate across the globe (Bouwer, 2011, IPCC, 2008)-7. Under the assumption that expansion of water infrastructure reduces the vulnerability of water resources to climate change (Watts et al., 2011), several bills were introduced in the U.S. Congress calling for feasibility studies relating to the construction of new dams (Christensen, 2014,-8 Feinstein and Boxer, 2015,-9 Huffman et al., 2015).

We conducted research on the Surkhandarya region of Uzbekistan, one of the most sensitive regions of Central Asia to climate changes, to clarify this topic and analyze the long-term dynamics of river runoff and climatic indicators.

Surkhandarya region lies in southern Uzbekistan, between 37°10' and 39°02' north latitude and 66°32' and 68°25' east longitude. It shares boundaries with Tajikistan in the east through the Bobotog and Hisar mountains in the northeast, Afghanistan in the south through the Amudarya valley, Turkmenistan in the southwest through the Kohitang ridge, and our Republic's Kashkadarya area by the river's branches. Hissar mountain range to the west and northwest. (E.N. Balasheva et al., 1962).

The Hisar mountain range in the Surkhandarya region occupies the majority of the Surkhandarya basin's mountain range. The Hissar range is considered the highest mountain range in the Surkhandarya basin, with some peaks in the range above 4500 m. There are multiple glaciers at such heights due to the cold temperatures. These glaciers are the source of the Surkhandarya's major tributaries. The Hissar mountain range is crucial in the creation of the Surkhandarya stream. The reason for this is that the runoff generated by the ridge's slopes accounts for at least 70% of the total runoff generated in the Surkhandarya depression's hilly region. (E.N. Balasheva et al., 1962).

The Boysun Mountains are the southwestern spurs of the Hissar Range, and their height reaches 4000 m

only in the north. The height of the Boysun Mountains drops dramatically as they move south. As a result, there are no rivers with a continuous flow in the Surkhandarya basin to the south of the right bank. The Kingguzar gauging station on the Sangardak River was the subject of the investigation. This river and this gauging station were purposefully chosen. The river empties into the Surkhandarya River, one of the Amudarya River's major tributaries. The hydropost is located on basin territory, with no manmade impacts on the river above this point. It is feasible to collect objective data on the hydrological regime of the Sangardak River based on the current regime observations of the Kingguzar hydropost. The Sangardak River is the right tributary of the Surkhandarya River; it is 106 kilometres long, discharges into the Surkhandarya River 155 kilometres from its source, and has a basin area of 932 square kilometres. (E.N. Balasheva et al., 1962).

Along with the mountains, there are plains in the Surkhandarya basin, which are generally located in the centre of the basin, between the mountains. The Surkhandarya valley is located between the Baysun and Bobotog ranges. It stretches from northeast to southwest and borders the Amudarya valley in the south. The depression is large, and the surface is undulating, with steps at places. The depression is a plain that slopes down to the centre and southwest. The Surkhandarya valley is virtually in the centre of it. Its size is 3-5 kilometres, and the first and second terraces are well built and noticeable. The Surkhandarya region's third and fourth terraces do not cover extensive regions and have relative heights of 4-10 and 10-20 metres. The valley's absolute height is 700 metres at the top of the foothills and 300 metres on the boundary with the Amudarya valley. Because of its location in the Republic of Uzbekistan's south, the Surkhandarya region's weather conditions differ from those of the republic's other regions. Surkhandarya is the only region of the country that has a subtropical climate. This allows for the cultivation of subtropical fruits and cotton varieties in the region. (E.N. Balasheva et al., 1962).

Looking at the climatic conditions of Surkhandarya, we can observe that precipitation is distributed unevenly in this basin, as it is in other Central Asian basins. This is because the region is encircled on three sides by mountains, and air masses originate from the south. If there is a lot of precipitation on the slopes of the mountains around the basin, there is comparatively little precipitation on the plains located in the centre of the basin. The lowlands around the confluence of the Surkhandarya and the Amu Darya receive the least precipitation in the basin. Rainfall increases to the north and northwest. Weather forecasts can also teach us this. As a result, the annual precipitation in Shorchi is 228 mm, near Zarchob - 495 mm, and in Shargun - 625 mm. As a result, as altitude increases, and neither does the amount of precipitation. Rainfall is scarce in the mountains to the west of the Surkhandarya depression. The moist air flow from the southwest enters the valley and strikes the mountains in the west in a meridional manner, causing rain to fall on the mountain slopes. It never rains on the mountain.

The moist air current climbs towards the mountains, cools, and produces a lot of rain as it travels north and northwest. As a result, precipitation on the Hisar mountain slopes ranges between 1200 and 1500 mm. (E.N. Balasheva et al., 1962).

The rainy season in the Surkhandarya basin lasts from November to May. During this time, the majority of the annual precipitation falls. The amount of days in March with an average rainfall of 15 mm or more in 12 hours distinguishes it from other months. This value is an average of 5 days in April. There were no days with an average rainfall of more than 15 mm in January, July, August, September, or October. When we divide this value by 365, we find that more than 15 mm of precipitation falls on 24 days of the year. (E.N. Balasheva et al., 1962).

Since the 1920s, meteorological data has been collected in the basin. These observations, however, were not carried out in full at all meteorological stations. As a result, we used data from weather stations in the Surkhandarya Basin as far back as possible in time to recent years, based on data availability. Approximately 40 meteorological stations and posts were operational in the Surkhandarya basin at various times. Weather stations are positioned at various heights, and the data from weather stations and posts change based on their location. The Urugli weather station, for example, is placed at the highest point (1800 m) above sea level. The Dzharkurgan meteorological station has the lowest elevation in relation to sea level. This meteorological station is 300 metres tall. Meteorological observatories Angorskaya, Manguzarskaya, Naushakharskaya, and Termezskaya are also positioned above 300-350 m absolute height. (E.N. Balasheva et al., 1962).

We measured meteorological parameters at Boysun (1249 m), Denov (516 m), and Sherabod (417 m), which are located near the river basins we researched, such as Sangardak, Sherabad, and Tupalang.

The number of meteorological elements observed at each weather station varies. Only a few readings were recorded at certain weather stations. The number of days with varying amounts of precipitation, for example, was only recorded at the meteorological stations Denov, Termez, Baysun, and Sherabad. Observations of atmospheric precipitation began in the 1930s and 1940s at the meteorological stations at Shorchi, Denov, Baysun, and Sherabad. These weather stations have observational data dating back to the year they were launched. The values of precipitation data observed at the Sherabad meteorological station differ from those observed at other meteorological stations. The main reason for this is that the station is in an arid location with little rainfall. The highest value from 1932 to the present at the Sherabad meteorological station corresponds to December 1991. During this time, 93 mm of rain fell during the month. Data on air precipitation have been available at the Boysun meteorological station since 1933. Later, at this meteorological station, further meteorological elements were observed. The most precipitation fell in March 1969, according to data from the Boysun

meteorological station, and totaled 197 mm. (E.N. Balasheva et al., 1962).

Water sources are extremely important in the Surkhandarya region. The region's hydrographic network is comprised of two major rivers and their tributaries. The confluence of the Topolangdarya and Karatog rivers forms Surkhandarya. Surkhandarya's natural-geographical region contains 35 rivers and streams with lengths of more than 20 kilometres. Their yearly water volume is 3.8 cubic metres per kilometre, with an average long-term water usage of 119 cubic metres per second. Surkhandarya and Sherobodarya are the two largest of these rivers. The confluence of Topolangdarya and Karatogdarya forms Surkhandarya. (V.L.Shults&R.Masharapov, 1969). Two major tributaries, the Sangardak and Khodjaipok rivers, flow into Surkhandarya on the right side. To the south of Khozhaypok, there are only a few streams and canyons that flow only when the water is high. The Baysunsoy, Akkopchigai, and Toshkoprik streams are the largest.

The river Sangardak village Kingguzar was the subject of our investigation in this research. The Sangardak River originates on the Gisar Range's south-western slope (at an altitude of 3800 m above sea level). The catchment area is 889 km², and the river basin average height is 2286 m. The river is known as Degikanora in its upper sections. The river is relatively thin in this section and flows through a valley with steep slopes. Several big and minor rivers run into the Sangardak River, with the rivers Kyzylsay, Shorchiob, and Molongur on the right and Khandiza and Nilu on the left. The Sangardak River receives most of its water from seasonal snow and groundwater. Maximum water flow is 44 m³/sec (in May), and 4.38-4.04 m³/s (November-January). The Sangardak River's average long-term water flow is 15 m³/sec, and the average runoff module is 17.0 l/sec per km². (Rasulov et al., 2003).

There are numerous methodologies and procedures for evaluating the impact of climatic elements on runoff variability, as well as the variability of precipitation and air temperature. The analogous approach was frequently employed in hydrometeorology to examine changes in runoff and meteorological data. (A.M. Vladimirov, 1990)

River types	Criteria for the distribution of rivers by types of sources		
	δ=	in % of annual flow	The month with the highest outflow
Rivers of glacier-snow feeding	≥1	≥38	VII, VIII
Rivers of snow and glacier feeding	0,99-0,27	40-17	V, VI
Snow feeding rivers	0,27-0,18	16-12	IV, V
Snow-rain fed rivers	0,17-0	13-0	III, IV, V

The genetic method of hydrograph construction was applied to the compilation of the runoff hydrograph. (A.M. Vladimirov, 1990).

The intra-annual distribution of precipitation and air temperature determines the hydrological regime of rivers and how it changes. The levels of river runoff and their water supply are impacted by variations in certain weather conditions. (V.L.Shults&R.Masharipov, 1969). The availability of precipitation during those times when precipitation delivers and creates the runoff

The most commonly used methodologies in hydrometeorology are statistical methods for estimating a long-term series of observations and assessing their availability and properties. (G.N. Trofimov, 1999). Statistical approaches in hydrology are sometimes the sole option to provide quantitative estimates of diverse hydrometeorological events or processes. This is due to the multifactorial character of hydrological and climatic events, in which a vast number of components impact the development of the final outcome, making it impossible to account for the complete effect. (U.B.Vinogradov, 1988). The assessment of changes in hydrometeorological features and their connection was done using a mixture of graphic curves of intra-annual precipitation and water flow distribution. (M.I.Getker et al, 1972) Sh.Sh. Mukhamedjanov, the author of this work, combined the intra-annual distribution graphs of precipitation and water discharge for the first and last periods of the data series. The master's thesis of M. Isaboeva in 2021 made use of the methodology for evaluating the overlap of schedules of intra-annual distribution of precipitation. (M. Isaboeva, 20121).

Calculating the likelihood of a series and its characteristics, such as the coefficient of variation, standard deviation, asymmetry coefficient, etc., is a typical technique for estimating a long-term series of data. (A.VRojdestvensky&A.I.Chebotarev, 1974) Taking into account the multifactor nature of river runoff formation, we calculated the standard deviation or the standard of the coefficient of variation to assess the variability of the observed data on air temperature, precipitation, and river runoff, (A.VRojdestvensky&A.I.Chebotarev, 1974) :

$$\sigma_x = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})^2}{n}}$$

which is a characteristic of the variability of the statistical series and is determined by the formula (A.VRojdestvensky&A.I.Chebotarev, 1974) :

Based on the observed data, we performed calculations of river runoff nutrition using V.L. Schulz's classification. (V.L.Shults, 1965):

characteristic of the given region, conforming to the long-term average data of the base period, is what defines the concept of water content of the year rather than river runoff. When we refer to the base period, we refer to the number of years up until the year from which one can count either a growth or a reduction in the values of the indicator under consideration. (A.R. Rasulov et al., 2003)

The average annual air temperature has been rising in recent years, according to an analysis of its dynamics

for the years 1960 to 2019. According to the analysis, the air temperature at the Boysun meteorological station starts to rise in the middle of the seventies. In the last 50 years, the air's temperature has risen by 1.0 to 1.5 °C. As shown in Figure 1, the average annual air temperature was 13 °C in the 1960s and 1970s. Beginning in the 1990s of the year 2000, the average annual air temperature started to noticeably rise to 13.5 °C or

more degrees. In recent years, the average annual temperature has consistently shown 14 °C or higher. The variability of the maximum and lowest temperature also significantly decreased from the 1970s to the most recent years as compared to the 1960s. The gap between the maximum and minimum average yearly temperatures, which in the 1960s varied from 2°C to 3°, has recently not exceeded 1.0° to 1.5°.

Figure 1. Dynamics of long-term air temperature values at the Boysun meteorological station

The average annual air temperature changed more significantly at the Denov weather station than it did at the Boysun weather station between 1960 and 2019. In Figure 2, the Denov meteorological station's annual average temperature has risen by 2.5°C to 3.0°C or more

in recent years. The variability of the maximum and minimum values of the yearly average temperatures at the meteorological station also points to a significant drop in recent years compared to the 1960s and the early 1970s.

Figure 2. Dynamics of long-term air temperature values at the Denov meteorological station

Based on data from the Boysun meteorological station for the years 1960 to 2019, an analysis of long-term precipitation fluctuations reveals that the trend

line of the average values of the recorded series of precipitation has remained essentially unaltered during the entire observed period (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Dynamics of long-term values of atmospheric precipitation at the Boysun meteorological station.

The uniform distribution of yearly precipitation, with a single exception in 1968 and 1969, and a dramatic fluctuation in the maximum and minimum values of the total annual precipitation, is a defining feature of the statistical series of observations from the 1960s. The values of the annual precipitation total in the 1970s and 1980s are more consistent, with no obvious changes between years in the maximum and minimum amounts. It is clear that precipitation had significant maximum and minimum changes from the 1990s to 2018 in terms of total annual precipitation. The amount of annual precipitation and its tendency to grow or decrease have not changed much overall over the whole observation period.

As a result, an analysis of the long-term dynamics of precipitation and air temperature in the Surkhandarya basin revealed that there have been some

changes in climatic conditions over the past few years, primarily manifested as a rise in air temperature.

An analysis of the long-term variations in the average annual water discharges of the rivers in the Surkhandarya basin failed to detect any shift in the average values of water discharges in either a downward or upward direction. But as the graph in Figure 4 demonstrates, the characteristics of water discharge fluctuations are changing. The frequency of both high-water and low-water years has grown during the past few years, as has the variance between the maximum and minimum water releases. The type of river feeding determines how the hydrological regime of the rivers in Central Asia is established. (V.L. Shults. 1965). The majority of Uzbekistan's rivers are fueled by snow-glacier and snow-snow combinations. One of the key elements affecting how mountain rivers produce their river flow is air temperature. (V.L. Shults. 1965).

Figure 4. Dynamics of long-term values of water discharge (m^3/sec) along the Sangardak River (King-Guzar)

The climatic circumstances that have been formed over many millennia, where the temperature and precipitation regimes give sub-zero temperatures and a significant amount of solid precipitation in the winter, are what cause the snow-glacial feeding of the rivers of Uzbekistan and Central Asia. 1965 (V.L. Shults). The formation of glaciers as a result of the accumulation of snow in mountainous locations ensures the flow of rivers in the summer beginning in May when the glaciers begin to melt. At the same time, the months of July and August have the highest expenses. The type of river

feeding is established using V.L. Schultz's classification based on the ratio of the river flow during certain months to the overall annual flow. 1965 (V.L. Shults). The function of glaciers in the creation of the intra-annual distribution of runoff is significant in the conditions of Central Asia, particularly in its southwest, where precipitation falls primarily in the winter-spring period and the summer is dry. The flood shifts closer to fall the more glacial there is in the river basin. Obviously, this metric should drop with a considerable decrease in glacial. According to G.E. Glazyrin, the river's long-term path. Soh has a glacier-snow supply, which,

according to V.L. Shults (V.L. Shults. 1965), has significantly diminished over the past 50–60 years. The type of food has also altered as a result. (G.E. Glazyrin, 2014). Our research on the Surkhandarya river basin's

nutrition revealed that, between the 1950s and the present, the ratio of river flow for the months of July through September to the overall annual flow started to decline, from 0.30 to 0.10, which corresponds to snow-glacial nutrition (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Change in the coefficient of the δ -indicator of the type of river feeding calculated according to the classification of V.L. Schultz for the Sangardak River.

According to the type of food indicator's results, the Sangardak River's type of food has changed from snow-glacial to snow-rain. The fundamental cause of this, as previously indicated, is the recent rise in air temperature.

the full observation period to determine what changes are occurring in the region in terms of precipitation and the hydrological regime of rivers. We chose distinctive years in the beginning of the observation period, in the middle, and at the end of the observed series to compare changes in these indicators (Figure 6).

We evaluated the intra-annual distribution of air temperature, precipitation, and water discharges across

Figure 6 shows the intra-annual distribution of air temperature for 1960 and 2019 at the Boysun weather station.

Figure 6 shows that in 2019, compared to 1960, an increase in air temperature is noticed in practically all months of the year. In particular during the winter, the average monthly air temperature rose from +3.6°C to +9°C in December and from +5.6°C to +7.3°C in January. One of the key contributing reasons to the cardinal shift in the precipitation regime, feeding regime, and river flow regime in winter at an altitude of 1200 metres above sea level is a rise in air temperature. Due

to the high temperatures, atmospheric precipitation primarily takes the form of rain, which also feeds the riverbed during this time. Even when precipitation is in the form of snow, the warm air temperatures cause the snow to melt fast, replenishing the river bed.

A review of the intra-annual distribution of precipitation between 1960 and 2019 at the weather stations in Boysun, Sherabad, and Denov revealed that there has been a little change in the maximum precipitation from winter to spring in recent years (Figure 7).

Figure 7 shows the intra-annual distribution of atmospheric precipitation at the Boysun weather station between 1960 and 2019.

Figure 8. shows the intra-annual pattern of precipitation for the year 2019 at the Sherabad weather station compared to 1960.

Figure 9 shows the intra-annual distribution of air precipitation at the Denov weather station between 1960 and 2019.

At meteorological stations situated at low altitudes, a discernible change in precipitation from the winter season towards spring is observed (Denov weather stations - 516 m above sea level and Sherabad - 417 metres above sea level). There is a slight shift at elevations greater than 1200 metres above sea level (Boysun weather station, 1249 metres above sea level),

although it is much less pronounced than at low altitudes. The average winter and summer air temperatures tend to drop with height, according to V.E. Chub (V.E. Chub, 2015). The regime of stable snow cover is substantially impacted by the winter's quick temperature rise. Deterioration occurs sooner, a stable snow cover takes longer to establish, and the duration of the event gets shorter (B.E. Tsarev, 2010). This is common of all

high-altitude regions, yet the higher you go, the less of an impact it has. There is a "concentration" of winter in time and even a minor rise in snowfall, according to early data for MS Oygaing. The problem is complicated, thus more research is necessary. However, it is clearly evident that as a result of climate and topography, retreating glaciers not only "hide" in more favourable orographic settings, but also "leave" in those where climate change (warming) is weaker. Thus, G.E. Glazyrin asserts that at altitudes greater than 1.5 km,

the trend of the average summer air temperature responsible for the melting of glaciers in the higher levels of the Pskem is decreased and even negative. (G.E. Glazyrin, 2014).

The hydrograph of the flow of rivers in the Surkhandarya basin changed as a result of the shift in precipitation from the winter to the spring seasons. Figure 10 displays a timetable of the Sangardak River's intra-annual water flow pattern for the years 1960 and 2019.

Figure 10. Intra-annual distribution of water discharges of the Sangardak River.

The greatest hydrograph flows in 2019 have migrated towards spring, as shown in the graph, compared to the 1960s. As shown in Figure 10, extensive river flow feeding in 2019 began from the end of February to the beginning of March, whereas river flow feeding began in April in 1960. If the peak flow in 2019 is distributed from March to mid-April, the peak flow in 1960 is distributed from April to June. The graph reveals that a new runoff maximum emerged from February to April, which was not shown on the 1960 figure. Aside from a substantial shift in the hydrograph from summer to spring, the annual distribution of water discharges shows a large rise in water discharges during floods. If the greatest flow of water during floods was 40 to 80 m³/s in 1960, it has been routinely 80-100 m³/s in recent years. The area of the 1960 hydrograph, as shown in the figure, only covers the right summer part of the 2019 hydrograph. This condition shows that the atmospheric precipitation regime and the river flow feeding regime have changed dramatically in recent years. The additional maximum flow of water in the river from February to April is created solely by winter and early spring rainfall and snowmelt. If the Sangardak River runoff supply belonged to the snow-glacial supply in the 1960s, it had shifted to the snow-rain supply by 2019 as a result of winter warming and an increase in the intensity of liquid precipitation.

A comparative assessment of the temperature regime according to its average annual values between years in the period from 1960 to 2019 showed an increase in all the observed weather stations in the region we studied. The values of average annual air temperatures recorded at the Boysun meteorological station for the period 1960-2019 increased their values by 1.0°C -

1.5°C. This increase reached its maximum level by 2001. By 2019, this growth was found to have continued. The minimum temperature was observed in 1972. According to the Denov weather station, it was found that since 1988 the air temperature has increased compared to the 1960s. A comparative assessment of the temperature regime according to its average annual values between years in the period from 1960 to 2019 showed an increase in all the observed weather stations in the region we studied. The values of average annual air temperatures recorded at the Boysun meteorological station for the period 1960-2019 increased their values by 1.0°C - 1.5°C. This increase reached its maximum level by 2001. By 2019, this growth was found to have continued. The minimum temperature was observed in 1972. According to the Denov weather station, it was found that since 1988 the air temperature has increased compared to the 1960s. An assessment of the intra-annual distribution of average monthly air temperatures showed an increase in air temperature in almost all months. In particular, in winter, the air temperature in 2019 increased by 1.6°C compared to the 60s. In summer periods, an increase in air temperature by 2°C or more can be traced in all months. The values of 27 °C in the month of July observed in 1960 moved to the month of June, the temperature of June 1960, which was 25 °C, in 2019 more corresponds to the month of May (23.6 °). In March, in recent years, the air temperature shows 14.1°C (2019) against 7°C in 1960. An assessment of the intra-annual distribution of average monthly air temperatures shows that at present (2019) the temperature regime of the spring period has increased its values by 2 °C or more and corresponds to the values of average monthly temperatures that were

traced in 1960 one month later. As V.E. Chub notes, “.....the trends in the average winter and average summer air temperatures decrease with altitude. The rapid increase in winter temperatures significantly affects the regime of stable snow cover.” (V.E. Chub, 2015). The shift of elevated air temperatures in recent years by one month towards winter leads to the melting of those snow reserves that in previous years melted 1 month later. As G.E. Glazyrin “Seasonal snow on glaciers, melting in the warm season, is involved in a rapid moisture cycle. Its remains that did not melt in the firn areas are transformed into firn, and then into ice, which participate in a slow moisture cycle. It is this approach that is usually used by hydrologists in mathematical modeling of the flow of mountain rivers”. Snow that has melted ahead of time does not have the opportunity at elevated temperatures to transform into firn and participate in a slow moisture cycle. In the above graphs of the intra-annual distribution of precipitation, it can be seen that in recent years there has been a shift in the maximum values of precipitation from the winter period towards spring. These changes in the redistribution of precipitation indicate a change in climatic conditions on the territory of Uzbekistan and the entire Central Asian region and its direct impact on the change in the hydrological regime of rivers. Although there are no large changes in the intra-annual distribution in the above graphs for air temperature, there is a tendency for an increase in air temperature in recent decades, which in one way or another have an impact on the intra-annual distribution of precipitation and river runoff. As our studies show, there are certain changes in the temperature regime of the region when considering the fluctuations of monthly data in the long-term context in January and February. As can be seen from the graphs in recent years, the air temperature in January has significantly higher values than in previous years, and especially in the 60s and 70s (Fig. 6). The warming of air temperature in winter leads to the fact that the amount of solid precipitation will decrease significantly and the amount of liquid precipitation will increase. As a result of the studies of a long-term series of observations of the dynamics of precipitation, it was found that in recent years there has been a shift in the maximum values of precipitation from winter to spring. This, in turn, leads to a significant change in the hydrological regime of the rivers, which consists in a tendency to shift the maximum flow from the summer periods of June-July to the spring in May-June (Fig. 10). A further shift in precipitation from winter to spring may lead to a shift in river flow to earlier periods, which will affect the problem of keeping the main flow of rivers planned for use.

Conclusion

Studies on changes in meteorological indicators and river hydrological regimes in the Surkhandarya river basin have revealed that there has been an increase in air temperature in recent years. An examination of the dynamics of average annual air temperature values from 1960 to 2019 reveals an increase in recent years. According to the data, the increase in air temperature at the Boysun meteorological station began in the mid-70s. Over the last 50 years, the average temperature has

risen by 1.0-1.5 degrees Celsius. The average air temperature in the 1960s and 1970s was 13°C; however, beginning in the 1990s, average annual air temperatures began to visibly rise to 13.5°C or higher; in recent years, average annual air temperatures have consistently showed 14°C or higher. At the same time, the fluctuation of maximum and lowest temperatures has dropped dramatically during the 1970s compared to the 1960s. If the difference between the maximum and minimum average annual temperatures ranged from 2°C to 3° in the 1960s, it has not exceeded 1.0° - 1.5° in recent years.

An examination of the long-term changes in precipitation from 1960 to 2019 reveals that the trend line of the average values of the recorded series of precipitation remains virtually unchanged during the whole observed period. The uniform distribution of annual precipitation with a single case in 1968 and 1969, a dramatic variation in the maximum and minimum values of total annual precipitation, is a characteristic indicator of the statistical series of observations from the 1960s. The sum of annual precipitation values in the 70s and 80s are more uniform, with no dramatic changes in maximum and minimum values between years. Precipitation fluctuated sharply between the 1990s and 2018, with maximum and minimum values of total annual precipitation varying dramatically. In general, there are no noteworthy variations in the amount of yearly precipitation and its tendency to rise or decrease over the whole observation period. An examination of the oscillations in the average annual water flows of the rivers of the Surkhandarya basin over a long period of time revealed no change in the average values of water discharges, either decreasing or increasing. However, as shown in the graph (Figure 4), the nature of oscillations in water discharges is changing. The disparity between maximum and minimum water discharges has increased in recent years, as has the frequency of both high-water and low-water years.

The hydrological regime of Central Asian rivers is determined by the type of river feeding. The majority of Uzbekistan's rivers are fed by snow-glacier and glacier-snow. One of the primary variables influencing the method of development of mountain rivers' runoff is air temperature. Our research on the feeding of the rivers of the Surkhandarya river basin revealed that, from the 1950s to the present, the ratio of river flow for the months of July-September to total annual flow began to fall from 0.30, corresponding to snow-glacial feeding, to 0.10, corresponding to snow and rain feeding.

The annual distribution of climatic data and water discharge demonstrates that maximum precipitation has shifted from winter to spring in recent years, while river flow has shifted from summer to spring. Problems with the region's water resources may occur as a result of such a redistribution of precipitation, air temperature, and river flow. The river flow that was generated by melting snow and glaciers will now be formed in the spring, with some throughout the winter months. These fluids will not be trapped by snow and glaciers, but will instead flow immediately into the river basin. Under

such conditions, the Central Asian region faces an escalation of water scarcity, particularly during the growth season of agricultural crops.

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